

Evaluation of collaborative concept mapping on students' attitude in secondary schools in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya

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Published online: 6th July, 2023

Abstract

Attitudinal aspects contribute positively to the overall student's affective characteristics and influence the students' achievement. The performance in Biology subjects in the Kenya National Examinations Council is below 55% and this has been attributed to the students' negative attitude towards science subjects. Past studies have indicated that the usage of concept maps has some positive attitudinal effects on students. Therefore, the study examined how computer-based collaborative concept mapping influences students' attitudes towards biology in selected secondary schools in Uasin-Gishu County, Kenya. The study compared the concept mapping learning technique with the conventional teaching methods with the aid of Solomon Four-Group design. The population were form-two students from eight secondary schools; four boys' and girls' extra-county schools in Uasin-Gishu County, Kenya. The study had a total of 345 students; 167 in the experimental group and 178 in the control group. At the onset, the study measured the attitudes using a conventional tool. The experimental groups were taught using CMapTools software in the computer laboratories while the control group were taught using the conventional approach. After the end of the study period, both groups took a post-test questionnaire on attitudes towards Biology. The data generated were entered into statistical software and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics (χ^2 and t-test) at $\alpha = 0.05$. At the beginning of the experiment, the statistics; $\chi^2 = 1.05$ ($p > 0.05$), and $t = -0.820$ ($p > 0.05$) for the attitudinal component items showed that there was no significant difference in attitudes between the groups. At the end of the experiment, the statistic $t = 0.106$ ($p > 0.05$) indicated that there were no significant differences in attitudes between the experimental groups. Thus, the attitudinal component of the two experimental groups was more or less similar. The study concluded that concept mapping has a significant effect on the students' attitudes. The study recommends that teachers should adopt and incorporate collaborative and computer-based systems in improving attitudes towards science education in Kenya.

Key words: Mind Mapping; Mindtools; Concept mapping; Student Attitudes; Learning outcomes.

1. Introduction

Biology in secondary school is central to many science-related courses such as medicine, pharmacy, agriculture, nursing, biochemistry and many others (Yusuf & Afolabi, 2010). Furthermore, the importance of STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) discipline to the nation's economy, calls for improvements in techniques for teaching mathematics and science education (Maltese & Tai, 2011). However, the conventional approach to teaching science education in schools has not only failed to effectively prepare students' science experience beyond schooling (La Velle *et al.*, 2003). Past research has critiqued the conventional approach to learning, for example, Savelsbergh *et al.*, (2016) reported that different teaching approaches have a significant effect on the students' general attitudes towards science education, while having a differential effect on the student's achievement (Schroeder *et al.*, 2007).

The advances in technologies have enabled various new learning approaches to situate students in environments and combine real-world and digital-world learning resources and allow for collaborative and shared learning experiences (Hwang *et al.*, 2011; Hwang *et al.*, 2014). These technologies induce changes in pedagogical practice (Serin, 2011) as the cognitive tools embedded in ICT and the pedagogical content knowledge provide a powerful driver for the knowledge transformation (La Velle *et al.*, 2003). Moreover, the use of mindtools in an educational setting has attracted the attention of educators (Chu *et al.*, 2009) as they facilitate critical thinking and high order learning (Kazantzis & Hadjileontiadou, 2021; Hwang *et al.*, 2011).

Mindtools such as concept mapping provide a ubiquitous learning experience and serve as an extension of the mind as they engage learners in constructive higher-order critical learning (Hwang *et al.*, 2011). Concept mapping represents a visual organization that categorizes and represents knowledge bases about a particular subject or related subjects and fosters the development of critical skills (Cooper & Zimmerman, 2020). In addition, concept mapping helps reduce students' cognitive load (Abbas *et al.*, 2018). Concept mapping is an effective knowledge construction tool that helps learners organize important concepts related to a core issue and their inter-relationship (Hwang *et al.*, 2014). Concept maps stimulate metacognition and are therefore widely perceived to positively encourage reflection and its associated processes (Harrison & Gibbons, 2013) and help in independent learning activities (Chiou, 2008).

The studies on concept mapping Maps have reported that it can improve learning outcomes (Sanchiz *et al.*, 2019). In an experimental study, Hwang *et al.*, (2011) revealed that concept mapping has a significant influence on learning perceptions and attitudes towards science courses. Other empirical studies have shown that concept mapping is an effective way of engaging students in meaningful learning, hence, improving comprehension and learning achievements (Amadiou *et al.*, 2010). Kaddoura *et al.*, (2016) also explored the impact of concept mapping through an experiment among nursing students. The study revealed that students taught through concept mapping had higher cognitive scores than the control group. Hay (2007) reported that deep, surface and non-learning outcomes could be observed directly from learners using concept mapping at the university level. Chiou, (2008) revealed that concept mapping significantly improves students' learning achievement compared to using a traditional expository teaching method. Wu *et al.*, (2013) affirmed that map-based collaborative learning enhanced students' innovative performance. Chen *et al.*, (2011) also observed that the students who were taught through concept mapping performed better than the control group.

A meta-analytical study reported that the concept mapping technique was associated with increased knowledge retention (Nesbit & Adesope, 2006). Hwang *et al.*, (2013) observed that concept – mapping positively impacts students' attitudes towards learning science courses. Further, a study on the use of concept mapping by university students pursuing engineering revealed that there were significant differences in learning outcomes with the experimental group having higher scores (Martínez *et al.*, 2013).

Although previous studies have reported the effectiveness of the concept mapping approach, it remains an open issue for investigating its effects on students' learning attitudes. There is a general tendency across studies on innovative teaching approaches to have positive effects, there is little clarity on how these interventions cause effects on outcome, and under what conditions (Savelsbergh *et al.*, 2016). And as elaborated by the foregoing reviews, there is a need to evaluate the different pedagogical Practicals used in science education at secondary school level.

The performance in Biology subject has not been satisfactory and has indicated by the reports the average scores (standard deviation) for the last four years are 58.37(35.16), 37.85(23.45), 51.38(23.26) and 55.32(20.65) marks (KNEC, 2020). This indicates an average pass mark in the subject. This trend also shows that only a small number of students achieve grades B and

above and indicates that many bright students may be locked out of science courses (Chebotib & Kering, 2021).

Several studies (Abbas *et al.*, 2018; Kaddoura *et al.*, 2016; Wu *et al.*, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2011) have highlighted the positive effects of concept mapping in the education setting. More so, at the university level as well as different disciplines (Hwang *et al.*, 2013; Amadiou *et al.*, 2010; Kaddoura *et al.*, 2016). However, there have been relatively few research studies that have evaluated the usefulness of concept mapping at the basic education level. Thus, the study explored how computer-based collaborative concept mapping can be applied in teaching biology concepts in secondary schools in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya.

Material and Methods

The primary aim of the study was to compare the effects of a concept mapping with conventional teaching technique on the acquisition and retention of concepts of respiration by students in selected secondary schools in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya. The null hypothesis for the study was that there is no significant difference in the attitudes towards biology subjects between students taught the concept of respiration using concept Maps and those taught using conventional methods.

Study Design: The study used the experimental design known as the Solomon four non-equivalent control group. A student attitudinal test (SAT) was given to both groups to gauge their attitudes towards biology. Data were collected at three points during the study between May 2019 and July 2020 and the baseline data was generated from the student attitude questionnaire before the teaching intervention.

Study Population: The study was located in eight schools in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya with a total of 345 form-two students drawn from the extra-county schools. Next, the 345 students enrolled in the experiment into either the experimental or control group. Done by randomly allocating the whole class into the intervention (computer-based concept mapping) or control (conventional teaching method) groups.

Study Procedures: The two teaching techniques were designed to facilitate the acquisition of concepts in the topic respiration and comparisons made based on its effects. The concepts to be included were; respiration, cells, food, energy, muscle contraction, conduct nerve

impulses, tissue repair, growth, organ function, mitochondria, cristae and enzymes. The concept of respiration in the experimental group was taught outside the normal class hours (5.00 pm-6.00 pm) in the computer laboratory while the control group was taught within their respective classes. Both approaches were expected to take one hour daily for a period of five days or 300 minutes in duration.

Conventional module: The control group (n = 178) were taught in a normal classroom setting by the subject teacher. This involved the preparation of a lesson plan using the standard teaching pack. The whole concept of respiration was taught in five lessons each lasting for one hour daily over a period of five days (300 minutes).

Concept mapping: The experimental group (n = 167) were taught using computer-based concept maps with each lesson lasting for one hour over the five days. The content for the lesson included CMapTools which were downloaded freely from <http://cmap.ihmc.us> and loaded into all the personal computers in the computer lab.

In the experimental group, the researcher and her assistants first explained why concept mapping is a useful tool for learning and how concept mapping can be used to show relationships among concepts, and then spent hours training students to draw concept maps in accordance with the procedure with the aid of the software, the students began by placing the general idea (respiration) at the top of the map. Figure 1 shows an illustration of a concept map.

Figure 1: Sample of a generated concept map

Source: Research Data (2020)

Outcome measures

Attitudinal aspects

This test consisted of twenty – questions with a five-point Likert type scale that evaluated the students based on the statement’s levels of agreement/disagreements (strongly agree, agree, indecisive, disagree, and strongly disagree).

Statistical Analysis

The data analysis was based on the Solomon four non-equivalent group design using the SPSS (version 20) statistical software package. First, the descriptive analysis was carried out and then the χ^2 - test and t-test were conducted at 0.05 significance levels. **Result**

Table 1(Appendix) shows the attitudinal aspects of the participants during the pre-test period which included the affirmative and their negated equivalent statements. Regarding biology as a subject, the respondents strongly affirmed that they found the biology subject interesting (Mean = 4.3933, SD = 1.0042) and were fascinated by the biology subject (Mean = 3.8933, SD = 1.277). Many respondents affirmed that they liked biology as a subject (Mean = 4.2303, SD = 1.1922), and the majority of the participants looked forward to biology lessons. The participants also affirmed that they enjoyed learning biology (Mean = 4.0899, SD = 1.2133)

and always looked forward to biology experiments (Mean = 3.9607, SD = 1.2728). The affirmative statements had χ^2 statistics ranging from 1.351 to 8.248 with $p > 0.05$ except for the statement 'I have good feelings towards biology'. This indicated that there were no significant differences in attitudes in both experimental and control groups. On the converse, the negated equivalent statements had most $p < 0.05$, which indicated statistical differences between the attitudes.

Table 2(Appendix) displays the attitudinal aspects of the participants towards concept mapping after the concept mapping and included the affirmative and their negated equivalent statements. The respondents affirmed that concept mapping was interesting (Mean = 4.3653, SD = 0.8527) and that the maps helped them understand biology (Mean = 4.1737, SD = 1.1138). Many respondents affirmed that concept mapping has made them creative (Mean = 4.1796, SD = 1.1370), while helping them to conceptualize (Mean = 4.4491, SD = 0.8407). The participants also affirmed that concept mapping made learning easier (Mean = 4.3174, SD = 0.9637) and has aided them in developing a positive feeling (Mean = 4.4551, SD = 0.7816). The statistics in Table 1 examined for any association between the study variables and sex of the student (experimental group) using the chi-square distribution. The affirmative statements had χ^2 statistics which ranged from 0.334 to 5.575 with $p > 0.05$ indicating no significant differences in attitudes in both the experimental and control group

Biology Aptitude Test Scores

Table 3: Comparison of biology test scores

Control group				
	N	Mean	SD	t-test
Pre-	82	2.9591	0.3180	-0.820
test	91	2.9236	0.2503	
Experimental group				
Post-	73	3.2575	0.2666	0.106
test	78	3.2532	0.2359	

*Significant at 0.05

The results as summarised in Table 3 shows the differences in attitudinal aspects based on the Solomon Four Group design. The mean pre-test item scores for the control group had a mean of 2.9591(0.31799) while those for the experimental group had a mean of 2.9236(0.25037). When the comparison was done, no significant differences emerged between the groups in the pre-test attitude scores ($t = -0.820$, $p > 0.05$). However, after the experiment, a higher mean was achieved by the experimental group with a mean of 3.2532(0.2359), while the

control group had a mean of 3.2575(0.2666). Thus, there were no significant differences in attitudes between the groups ($t = 0.106, p > 0.05$).

Discussion

The results showed that there were no significant differences in attitudes between the groups, thus the attitudes of the students were comparatively similar. In the post-test examination of attitudes, there were no significant differences between experimental groups thus implying that the groups were significantly not different from each other. The findings show that the students held a positive attitude towards concept mapping as illustrated by higher attitudinal scores for the post-test (Mean = 3.25, SD = 0.25) versus pre-test (Mean = 2.95, SD = 0.28). The findings conform to those of previous studies that indicated that the application of concept mapping technologies in learning activities has the potential to inspire students' extrinsic motivation and possibly enhance learning outcomes (Hwang *et al.*, 2014; Amadiou *et al.*, 2010).

Empirical studies have shown that students using concept mapping have better learning outcomes when compared to the conventional learning technique in several contexts (Chiou, 2008; Cañas *et al.*, 2012; Kaddoura *et al.*, 2016). These findings suggest cognitive gain and knowledge retention and mastery of biology concepts implies that the study participants can learn the theoretical abstracts that may be taught using concept mapping (Martínez *et al.*, 2013). Concept mapping employs concepts and propositions as central elements in structuring knowledge and creating meaning while translating complex concepts into visual representations (Cañas *et al.*, 2017).

Conclusion

The major findings confirm the previous research in demonstrating the superiority of concept mapping and this is a valuable finding. Given the ongoing debate on the increasing use of mindtools, the findings provide evidence that concept mapping is as effective as conventional methods when used to teach secondary school students. Therefore, Computer-based instruction should be embraced as a potentially valuable teaching tool, especially given the possibilities of self-study and distance education.

Recommendation

The study was limited by its smaller sample size and homogeneity which would potentially affect the generalisation of study findings; thus, the findings must be interpreted with caution. Any future studies should desire a larger sample with a corresponding heterogeneous population. Despite this limitation, the strength of this study lies in the use of a rigorous design that addressed many of the flaws evident in previous research. The study contributes to the introduction and use of the concept mapping in science education in a secondary school setting in Sub – Saharan Africa and thus it provides a foundation for further studies to explore the concept.

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